

USE OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF SPECIAL TRANSLATION

F.B. MATTIYEVA

Samarkand State Institute

foreign languages

Independent researcher

+998937236400

feruzamattiyeva@gmail.com

Annotation: *Special or functional professional competence is the ability to carry out activities at a high professional level. Special professional competence consists not only of special knowledge, but also of the implementation of this knowledge; Social competence is knowing how to carry out additional activities, knowing how to do it in cooperation. Personal competence - knowing the ways of self-development and self-expression (the specialist plans his activities, makes independent decisions, works with information and on himself). Individual competence is knowing how to manage oneself, preparing for professional development and creating professional innovations.*

Keywords: *Social and professional competence, personal competence. special or functional competence, expert planning of activities, decision-making.*

A.K. Markova is a pedagogic scientist who most often searched for the basics of professional competence of teacher's work. According to A.K. Markova, the teacher's work becomes competence. When the teacher performs his activities at a high enough level and teaches and educates students at a high level. Along with these foundations, the teacher's professional competence is divided into four:

Special or functional professional competence is the ability to carry out activities at a high professional level. Special professional competence consists not only of special knowledge, but also of the implementation of this knowledge; Social competence is knowing how to carry out additional activities, knowing how to do it in cooperation;

Personal competence - knowing the ways of self-development and self-expression (the specialist plans his activities, makes independent decisions, works with information and on himself).

Individual competence is knowing how to manage oneself, preparing for professional development and creating professional innovations. At the same time, the teacher's

knowledge should be enriched with news, and his psychological and pedagogical qualities should be at a high level.

The structure and content of professional competence consists of two main components. Professional competence is a characteristic of knowledge, skills and experience, and planning is a factor that makes the work of a specialist. In scientific articles on the problems of professional competence published by various authors, it is noted that creative research is one of the main qualities. This is a very important aspect, especially for teachers of vocational education, and special emphasis is placed on the issue of creativity in the professional competence of a specialist. Creative outlook and fearless creative activity, even if it is life issues; It is personal responsibility for the growth and all-round development of the "student" and his/her training to improve freely and to organize it. Modern society requires the educational system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the 2017-2021 action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a pool of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" was set. A competent pedagogue - who is he? Questions arise, such as how the process of its formation takes place. In this context, it is important to define the meaning of the concepts "competence" and "competence". Not every teacher knows what "competence" means and how it differs from "competence". The concept of "competence" includes education, skills, abilities and experience of a pedagogue. In other words, it is his ability to perform a certain type of work. Actually, both terms are similar. Competence refers to the totality of knowledge and its availability in people, while competence refers to the level of use of knowledge in the work process. There are several approaches to the definition of competencies: - In the American approach, competencies are considered as patterns of employee behavior. If the employee has the necessary skills and knowledge, he will show good results. - In the European approach, competencies are seen as a description of work tasks and expected work results, that is, the ability to act in accordance with accepted standards. In the State Educational Standard of General Secondary Education, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 187 of April 6, 2017, the concept of competence is defined as the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities in daily activities. In order to perform the functions correctly, the pedagogue must know the concept of competence and competence, know in which direction to move in order to develop in all respects and grow professionally. Professionalism and competence are similar terms, but they have different meanings. Professionalism means not only certain knowledge, but also the attitude to work, specific features of work. The

developed competences are immediately noticeable, because the professional pedagogue tries to develop his skills, strives to achieve certain goals and results, produces working values, and these usually correspond to the standard of the work process. Competence has a somewhat complicated meaning, because it requires not only the presence of knowledge, but also the ability to apply it.

Competence can only be determined during extensive evaluation and observation. Concepts of professionalism and competence have common features.

It should be noted that people who fully meet the established requirements and standards do not always become true professionals, because some do not know how to apply knowledge in practice, so such pedagogical activity remains ineffective. It is appropriate to divide professional pedagogical competences into separate types: - Special pedagogical competence - having sufficient knowledge to carry out pedagogical activity at the necessary level. In addition, the pedagogue's ability to adequately assess his professional level and determine his development as a specialist depends on this type. - Social pedagogical competence - the level of social competence determines the ability of a pedagogue to effectively build relationships with colleagues, plan joint actions. Effective communication skills, pedagogical culture and responsibility for work results - all this is included in the concept of social pedagogical competence. - Personal pedagogical competence is the ability to rationally organize pedagogical work, time management, striving for personal growth are its main components. Workers with a high level of personal pedagogical competence are less prone to burnout and are able to work under time pressure. Each type of competence includes a set of skills, knowledge, and abilities. In pedagogues, they appear at different levels. It is possible to determine how this or other competencies have been developed by paying attention to the indicators of his behavior in the performance of service duties. How is competence formed? The main thing for the formation of the teacher's competence is special professional education. In the future, knowledge and skills gained in practice will supplement the level of initial competence. All this can be presented in the form of a formula: Competence = I know + I can do + I want + I do. Formation of professional competence is a gradual and continuous process. We can divide it into the following stages: 1. Obtaining special information. 2. To acquire practical knowledge and skills. 3. Training, special courses and training. 4. Having professional experience. 5. Achieving professionalism in one's field. 6. Competence of the pedagogue improves by gaining experience, acquiring new knowledge and skills. The success of the process largely depends on the personal characteristics of the pedagogue. How to quickly and independently check that the teacher is working well? How to assess compliance? Evaluating the competence of pedagogues is a system consisting of the following components: - the

level of competence of pedagogues - benchmark criteria are used for evaluation; - labor productivity and work quality; - compatibility of personal characteristics with the field of education; - availability of additional skills; - desire for personal growth and professional development. When evaluating the competence of teachers, the effectiveness of working based on behavioral indicators is taken into account. This is precisely what the differences between competence and competence mean.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг —Таълим тўғрисидаги Қонуни // Баркамол авлод – Ўзбекистон тараққиётининг пойдевори. – Тошкент; Шарқ, 1997. – Б. 2-29.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг —Кадрлар тайёрлаш миллий дастури // Баркамол авлод – Ўзбекистон тараққиётининг пойдевори. – Тошкент; Шарқ, 1997. – Б. 31-61.
3. Tim Newfields, Teacher development and assessment literacy, Authentic Communication // Proceedings of the 5th Annual JALT Pan-SIG Conference. May 13-14, 2006. Shizuoka, Japan; Tokai University College of Marine Science. –P.48 - 73).
4. Fulcher G. Assessment literacy for the language classroom // Language Assessment Quarterly , 9(2). –P.113-132
5. Алимов Ф.Ш. Инглиз тилида ёзув компетенциясини шакллантириш (нофилологик факультетлар мисолида): Автореф. дисс. ... пед. фан. док. – Тошкент, 2018. –44 б.
6. Alderson J. & Bachman L. Assessing listening p.x. Cambridge University Press. – 2001.